

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW: A STUDY OF MALAY MYTHICAL CHARACTERS IN REFLECTING ATTITUDES FROM PRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This paper examines the study of Malay mythical characters in reflecting attitudes. The study of mythical characters is carried out in various languages and nations around the world. This mythical character is considered by traditional society as something that really happened in the past. Myths are also said to be ancient stories that are considered true, especially those that contain elements of concepts or beliefs about the early history of the existence of tribes and natural events. Among the forms of Malay mythic character studies that are often examined from a pragmatic perspective include positive attitudes (hardworking, obeying orders, defending rights, keeping promises) and negative attitudes (stupidity, deception, fights, bad luck). Therefore, the collection of past studies on the attitudes of Malay mythical characters from a pragmatic point of view needs to be examined more systematically. This collection of more organized studies uses a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) methodology which is based on certain criteria in the PRISMA protocol for the selection of articles involving four large databases, namely Scopus, Science Direct, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. A total of 14 articles were selected and eligible for the study findings. The purpose of the selected article is to find that the Malay mythic characters studied in Malaysia are Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk, Mak Andak, Mak Si Randang, Si Dagang, Si Luncai, Puteri Santubung and Puteri Sejinjang, Mat Jenin, Puteri Gunung Ledang, and Badang. Data sources selected from previous studies are various types of Malay mythical characters. The pragmatic perspective in this SLR describes the latest pragmatic studies, which can be developed more widely as a variation of language studies that should be studied in depth by future researchers.

Keywords: Malay Mythical, Characters, Attitudes, Pragmatic Perspective, Systematic Literature Review

1. INTRODUCTION

Character is a trait (of a person) outwardly and inwardly that includes character, habits, behavior, soul and thoughts (Kamus Dewan Edisi Keempat, 2016). A character is an individual self-representative in a narrative or dramatic art such as novels, plays and films (Baldick, 2001; Trumble & Stevenson, 2003; Childs & Fowler, 2006). Usually, there are two types of characters that are highlighted in a narrative, namely the main character and the side character. Each of these characters has its own role to play in a story (Ismail et al., 2023).

Character can be further broken down into eight cores, such as:

- a) **Main character:** The main character is the character who plays the main role in a story. Usually, the main character faces various disturbances and obstacles such as misunderstandings in the story so that the readers can learn and understand the true meaning of life (Rokimin, 2008). The author also focuses a lot on the main character, in addition to classifying the character as a protagonist or antagonist.
- b) **Protagonist character:** Protagonist character is a character admired by readers because this character reflects good norms and values such as honesty, humility, cleverness, independence, and self-defense (Burhan, 2015; Imron, 2017; Kim et al., 2020; Muller et al., 2020).
- c) **Antagonist character:** Antagonist character is a character that is opposite to the protagonist character because this character often creates conflict and opposes the protagonist character (Imron, 2017; Grizzard et al., 2020; Tu & Brown, 2020).
- d) **Round characters:** Round characters are the main characters developed by the author, but are depicted as having normal human characteristics in everyday life, that is, neither completely evil nor completely good (Asih, 2013; Wibisono, 2013; Fei, 2015; Tucker, 2016). Frank (2013), on the other hand, describes the round character as having a variable nature and cannot be predicted by the reader because there are times when the reader will be surprised by the behavior of the character in question.
- e) **Dynamic characters:** Dynamic characters are described as characters that develop and show character changes from the beginning of the narrative until the end of the narrative (Nikolajeva, 2002; Sigar, 2008; Jones, Quinn, & Koskinen, 2020). Dynamic characters are also described as full of energy and usually undergo changes according to the development of the story (Anggoro, 2018).
- f) **Flat characters:** Flat characters are introduced by the author through one personal aspect only (Sweeney & Fry, 2012; Wibawa, 2013). For example, the bully character, the reader will be faced with only negative behavior throughout the story. Therefore, the reader is not surprised by the character's behavior, because the reader can already anticipate any possibility that he does based on the personal characteristics set by the author (Urvantsey, 2019).
- g) **Static character:** A static character is a character that does not experience any changes throughout the course of the narration (Moezzi et al., 2017; Borisová, 2020). According to Bridgman, Cummings and Ballard (2019), this kind of character is thick with the attitude towards behavior highlighted by the author from the beginning of the story until the end of the story.
- h) **Secondary characters:** Secondary characters are also known as supporting characters that are embodied by the author as a complement in a story to support the actions of the main

character (Putnam et al., 2018). This character also moves along with the main character in a narrative or story (Vuong et al., 2020).

From the point of view of the character of the Malay myth, it can be divided into two, namely in the form of story or narrative and in the form of non-story or non-narrative. Among the characters that are embodied such as Pak Pandir, Awang Lurus, Pak Kaduk, Pak Belalang and Lebai Malang have been classified in folk literature (form of humorous stories). These characters are also found in old poetry which is seloka (non-story or non-narrative form). Despite the existence of these characters, in the form of jokes and jokes, their representative attitudes are the same. This kind of thing has made Malay mythical characters, very interesting to study.

Research on Malay myths such as seloka and Malay jokes has been carried out by past researchers. For example, Winstedt (1969), Johnson (2006), Peng and Ishak (2009), Zakaria (2015), Ismail, Bakar, and Effendy (2018) and Jabar (2019). This character is often associated with negative behavior and attitudes. For example, Winstedt (1969) has described Pak Kaduk's character as "foolish-shit" because this character has been described as having stupid qualities, lacking a brain because he is motivated by greed and wanting to make a profit. Because, his arrogant nature has caused him to lose his thinking power and finally befall an unfortunate fate. A recent writing by Ismail, Bakar, and Effendy (2018) has refuted the claims of Winstedt (1969) because this PK does not refer to negative behavior only. However, this character also embodies positive traits such as "following orders" and "keeping promises". According to Ali (2013), this Malay mythical character is not only integrated into the soul of the Malay community, but it is a vessel for the preservation of customs, character building, teaching the knowledge of love, entertainment, faith and defence. Therefore, a critical discussion needs to be done to see more clearly the attitude of the mythical character of Malay jokes in a special medium, namely Systematic Literature Review (SLR) through the views of past researchers. In summary, this SLR study is based on the research questions, namely:

- i. Can attitudes in Malay myths reflect the attitudes of society in Malaysia?
- ii. What type of pragmatic theory is used in the study of Malay mythical attitudes?

2. OBJECTIVES

This study aims to examine the literature related to Malay mythic character attitudes from a pragmatic point of view using a SLR methodology.

3. METHODS

Several past studies with the same research scope are systematically analyzed and combined in order to determine the pattern or results of the study as a whole. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses) 2020 checklist guide was used during this study. In addition, steps in synthesizing past studies (Tawfik et al., 2019; Caverro-Redondo et al., 2019) were also identified and used in this analysis. Figure 1 shows the article selection process.

Figure 1: Article selection process

Access or search strategy: The databases used in the article or journal selection process are Scopus, Science Direct, Web of Science and Google Scholar. Next, articles or journals from 2015 to 2023 were downloaded and analyzed. Based on the research questions that have been formed, there are five main keys in the Malay language such as pragmatics, attitudes, characters, myths, and Malay myths to guide the exploration of other key word variations. Meanwhile, pragmatics, attitudes, characters, myths, and Malay myths are key words in English. The results of the search string without filtering through the database in the selection of articles are as follows (refer to Table 1).

- a) Inclusion and exclusion criteria: Empirical studies relevant to the title, which is the study of Malay Mythical Characters in Reflecting Attitudes from a Pragmatic Angle between 2015 and 2023, are the main criteria in the selection of articles. However, only articles in Bahasa Melayu were selected because these articles are closer to the Malaysian context. Articles that did not fit the title were excluded (refer to Figure 1)

4. RESULTS

The results of the study are based on the research questions, namely, (i) Is the attitude of the Malay myth able to reflect the attitude? and (ii) What type of pragmatic theory is used in the study of Malay mythical attitudes? can be formulated based on the following table:

Table 1: Eligible articles to be synthesized

No.	Researcher	Malay mythical characters studied	Theoretical Framework or Approach	A pragmatic perspective
1.	Subet, Nadarajan, & Abang Suhai, (2015)	Pak Pandir and Ma'Taroi	Character Comparison	Explaining the negative ideology emitted in the humorous characters of Pak Pandir and Ma'Taroi to some extent form a picture of negative attitudes in the employment industry
2.	Podoli and Ghazali (2016)	Pak Pandir	Connotative and denotative approaches	Discussing Pak Pandir's attitude can be used as a satire to the community from a political and social point of view.
3.	Rusli (2018)	Pak Pandir and Lebai Malang	Adaptation Theory	Elaborating Pak Pandir and Lebai Malang's humorous stories into the form of visual art works so as to successfully enrich and dignify them in the form of political art
4.	Jabar (2019)	Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk, Mak Andak, Mak Si Randang, Si Dagang, Si Luncai, Mat Jenin	Functional Sphere Theory (Benefit Sphere)	Explaining that icons in Malay seloka also bring a good image to the audience
5.	Hamdan & Annuar (2020)	Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk, Pak Belalang dan Si Luncai	Comprehensive approach	Rejecting allegations about 'Lazy Malays' and 'Stupid Malays'
6.	Rusli & Zali (2020)	Si Luncai	Adaptation Theory	Relating Si Lucai's character to the local political context
7.	Jabar & Ghazali (2021)	Pak Pandir dan Pak Kaduk	Theory of <i>SPEAKING</i>	Proving that the reading of the poem basically only finds elements of humor and stupidity in the characters of Mr. Pandir and Mr. Kaduk, but based on the theory used, it manifests a positive impact on the communication innovation process of the Malay community.
8.	Osman & Jalaluddin (2014)	Singapore was struck by the Sword	Relevance theory, ad hoc expansion and narrowing	Analyze the criticism of the effects of systemic injustice and political tyranny at the time.
9.	Osman & Jalaluddin (2015)	The Myth of China-Melaka Relations	Relevance Theory in Cognitive Relevance Principles and	Explain the strength and power of the king or kingdom of Malacca at that time.

			Communicative Relevance Principles	
10.	Osman & Jalaluddin (2018)	The proposal of Puteri Gunung Ledang	Relevance Theory, ad hoc and Cross-Reference Framework approaches	Explaining his desire to marry the Princess of Gunung Ledang is an unrealistic act.
11.	Osman & Jalaluddin (2020)	The bravery of Badang	Relevance Theory, ad hoc and Cross-Reference Framework approaches	Explaining that brave and strong people will be respected as well as Validating the sovereignty of the origin of the Malay kings
12.	Daud & Subet (2021)	Puteri Santubong and Puteri Sejinjang	Relevance Theory	Proving that the fight between Puteri Santubong and Puteri Sejinjang can relate to the local political context
13.	Daud, Subet & Pawi (2023)	Pak Kaduk	Relevance Theory	Interpreting the expression “Aduhai malangnya Pak Kaduk, ayamnya Menang Kampung tergadai” with the context of local politics
14.	Ismail, Bakar, & Effendy (2018)	Awang Lurus, Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk, Si Luncai	A Humanistic Psychological Approach	Categorize attitudes and characters based on physiological needs, safety needs, love needs, self-esteem needs and the need to seek self-perfection.

5. DISCUSSION

Critical analysis is needed to explain the importance of the study that needs to be conducted as an alternative study. According to Rahimin (2019), critical analysis is also known as a research gap, so the task of the researcher is to discuss the gaps found in previous studies in a clear and detailed way to find commonalities and differences between the studies. Baba (2016) added, the concept of identifying the strengths and weaknesses of previous studies makes it easier for the writer to plan the study, choose a theoretical framework and determine the research methodology to suit the study to be carried out. The study of Ismail, Bakar and Effendi (2018) has proven that the negative perspective on the attitudes of Awang Lurus, Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk and Si Luncai in Malay jokes can be refuted through an approach in the field of psychology which is humanistic. This study has rejected the claims of previous researchers (Crwafurd, 1820; Bottoms, 1965; Winstedt, 1969; Maier, 1988) who called the character of Malay humour as straight, stagnant, stupid, blind to the king, uncivilized and unintelligent. This study has proven that characters such as Awang Lurus, Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk and Si Luncai have reflected positive attitudes and characters such as being light-hearted, obeying orders, being brave, defending rights and keeping promises.

It is different from the research data (Desa, Zali, & Muhammad, 2017; Norazizan & Annuar, 2018) because it is more multidisciplinary. These studies have attempted to link the current political scene with the production of creative works such as music and fine arts. The findings of Desa, Zali and Muhammad (2017) have shown that Nor Azizan Rahman Paiman's painting produced in 2008 has implicitly criticized the political figure Anuar Ibrahim. Although, this painting is not drawn as a portrait of the real Anuar Ibrahim. But, with the help of the sentence "I will throw the file at their face if the judges are not fit to hear my case" and the date "July 5" in the painting has helped the

audience to associate this painting with Anuar Ibrahim. In line with the findings of the data (Desa, Zali, & Muhammad, 2017). Rusli (2018) and Rusli and Zali (2020) studies, on the other hand, have been able to link mythical characters in Malay jokes such as Pak Pandir, Lebai Malang and Si Luncai with the political scene in Malaysia. This study has used the visual art exploration method as an interpretation of political issues. Images such as clowns, Jokers, calendars, BERSIH rally participants, coca wood beads, kabung fruit, pepper mash, machetes, pumpkins, deer, human figures with turbans and Guy Fawkes masks have been used by painters to relate the Malay mythic characters Pak Pandir, Lebai Malang and Si Luncai, political scene and fine art painting. Nevertheless, the data of drawings in writing (Rusli, 2018; Rusli & Zali, 2020) are more general without touching on the names of political figures in Malaysia, such as the research data of Desa, Zali and Muhammad (2017).

The main data of this study are Malay mythic characters taken from Malay jokes such as Awang Lurus, Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk and Si Luncai. Various studies have been conducted by past researchers (Subet, Nadarajan, & Abang Suhai, 2015; Rohani & Palodi, 2016; Rusli, 2018; Jabar, 2019; Hamdan & Annuar, 2020; Rusli & Zali, 2020; Jabar & Ghazali, 2021) using the data. Previous studies such as Jabar (2019) and Jabar and Ghazali (2021) were found to be close to the study of Ismail, Bakar and Effendy (2018) in the field of Humanistic Psychology. This is said to be so because this study also confirmed that characters in humorous stories have a positive attitude (Subet, Najarajan, & Abang Suhai; Rohani & Palodi, 2016). These studies have explained that the character of Malay jokes can be absorbed in the current context such as the state of the industry (employment sector), the economy (the difference in rubber prices in Peninsular Malaysia and the Sabah Region), social aspects (relating the standard of living of workers and employers in the issue of leave) as well as the political aspect (criticism of the medium of television is usually dominated by the ruling political party). However, this study argues that writing (Subet, Najarajan, & Abang Suhai; Rohani & Palodi, 2016) is not analyzed and provided with an authoritative theory or approach. According to Jalaluddin (2002), in qualitative research theory is needed because it is a place to cling to solve problems and describe research data.

As a result of awareness of the importance of theory or approach in a study (Osman & Jalaluddin, 2014, 2015, 2018; Ismail, Bakar and Effendy, 2018; Jabar, 2019; Jabar & Ghazali, 2021) have used various theories to support their research findings. The latest study by Daud and Subet (2021) is more forward because it has been able to relate Relevance Theory, the characters of Puteri Santubong and Puteri Sejinjang and the political scene in Malaysia. This study can be said to be a pilot study using language and linguistic theory for a multidisciplinary study. This study has improved the study of Malay myths by Osman and Jalaluddin (2014, 2015, 2018, 2020). This study argues that the extraction of the true meaning in Relevance Theory analysis should not be wasted. Based on this true meaning, the process of combining with the current context is more authoritative to be absorbed. However, this study is more focused on serious genres such as history (or genealogy) and epic. Starting point from these studies has opened a research gap on the study of myths involving elements of humor. According to Ahmad (2007), humorous stories such as Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk and Lebai Malang actually contain cynical and sharp satirical elements that are

specifically aimed at certain parties. In the context of this study, the political scene will be seen. According to Osman (2007), funny characters such as Pak Pandir, Pak Kaduk and Lebai Malang recorded in the 19th century are relevant to the socio-political situation of Malays in the 21st century.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the studies of Malay mythical characters in reflecting attitudes from a pragmatic point of view give the identity of attitudes to a society, can provide an overview of the situation and time of an event, can show attitudes or elements of heroism and serve for universal unity. This article also suggests to future researchers to analyze Malay myth data by relating the current environment, for example the state of the country's politics, economy, or current social environment.

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